

Applying Project-Based Learning Method in Teaching the Subject of Educational Economics for Students of Education

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Abstract:

Researching the relationship between economics and education is a crucial task for students in the field of Education to meet the demands of modern society. Key skills include analyzing, developing financial plans in education, and assessing the feasibility of educational projects. There are various methods for teaching educational economics, with active learning methods gaining significant attention. This study explores theoretical aspects of project-based learning and the expected learning outcomes for this course. The article proposes a three-stage process for applying project-based learning in teaching educational economics. In the first

stage, instructors define and communicate the project's objectives to students. In the second stage, students execute the project under the instructor's guidance, applying learned knowledge to tackle project challenges and fulfill objectives. The final stage involves assessment, where instructors evaluate student performance based on the course's goals. Applying project-based learning in educational economics instruction has positive impacts, encouraging student engagement, fostering self-directed learning, and developing problem-solving and critical-thinking skills, all of which align with societal expectations.

Keywords: *Project-Based Learning, Education Major, Economics of Education, Teamwork.*

Introduction

The subject of Economics of Education explores the relationship between education and economics, analyzing how economic factors affect the education system and vice versa. The content of the course includes concepts related to the cost of education, financial investment in education, human resource development, economic development, and measuring the impact of education on the economy. The goal of the Economics of Education course is to enable students to analyze investment costs in education, the relationship between the education system and economic development, as well as educational issues within an economic context. To achieve this goal, instructors apply

various active learning methods to help students apply theoretical knowledge to practice.

The project-based learning method, proposed by Kilpatrick, is considered suitable for the requirements of the Economics of Education course, from the perspective of Edward L. Thorndike's connection theory. According to Kilpatrick (1926), learners in a given situation exhibit various behaviors. He argued that an individual's behavior depends on how their needs are satisfied. If stimuli lead to satisfaction or disappointment, the learner's response will be closely linked to their actions. Kilpatrick believed that an individual's intellectual ability plays a role in directing their activities toward achieving goals that provide satisfaction. The

individual's behavior is goal-directed, creating satisfaction of their needs and generating a learning process. Therefore, learning motivation connects the individual's readiness to act consciously in order to achieve the goals they have set. The learning process begins with a clear objective for the activity, followed by exploration and contemplation on how to achieve that goal, practical action, and personal satisfaction upon reaching the goal, which in turn facilitates the learning process (Kilpatrick, 1918, 1926; Beineke, 1998).

The Project-Based Learning (PBL) method has also attracted attention from many researchers in the field of education, thanks to its effectiveness in enhancing learning skills and developing critical thinking. Other authors, such as Harasym et al., argue that using project-based methods can stimulate critical thinking and foster the moral development of students (Harasym et al., 2013). Research by Schmidt, Rotgans, and Yew continues to emphasize the important role of project-based learning in activating prior knowledge and promoting the understanding of new information. They suggest that working in small groups not only encourages collaboration but also enhances long-term retention for each student (Schmidt et al., 2011). Sutinen (2013) compared Kilpatrick's project method with Dewey's problem-solving method, pointing out that while both methods emphasize learning through action, they have different goals and approaches (Sutinen, 2013). Bilgin and Karakuyu identified that students engaged in PBL perform better and have a more positive attitude toward science teaching. They found that project-based learning not only improves academic achievement but also strengthens students' confidence in their teaching abilities (Bilgin et al., 2015). Additionally, several authors have demonstrated the effectiveness of project-based learning in teaching subjects such as Mathematics and Science, including Jacques and Walters (Jacques, 2017; Wilhelm et al., 2008).

The application of project-based learning (PBL) in the Economics of Education course not only helps students gain a deep understanding of theoretical concepts but also fosters essential skills such as critical thinking, teamwork, and

problem-solving abilities. Through practical projects, students have the opportunity to apply their knowledge to real-world situations, develop creativity, and raise awareness of the role of education in society. This process equips them with the necessary skills to address challenges in the field of educational economics in the future. The article discusses several theoretical issues regarding project-based learning, such as its characteristics, process, and implementation in teaching the Economics of Education course for students majoring in Education. A specific project is used to help students understand financial investment in education and determine supply and demand in the field of education.

Research Results

Project-Based Learning in Teaching

Concept of Project-Based Learning in Teaching

According to Michael Knoll, Kilpatrick's project method focuses on the learning process of students. However, the teaching activity of the teacher is not clearly defined within this method. The central idea of project-based learning is the development of the students' spirit and cognition. Therefore, the issue lies in how the teacher organizes the teaching activity so that the learning process follows the project-based method, which has not yet been fully clarified (Campbell, 1995). However, Kilpatrick (1918) argues that the teacher's role is to support the learning process to develop the students' awareness. This means the teacher acts as a guide, either directly or indirectly, to help students develop their cognition. The teacher's task is to create events that encourage students to participate in the learning process and achieve the set goals (Kilpatrick, 1918, 1926; Beineke, 1998; Tenenbaum, 1951).

Based on the perspectives on learning and the role of teachers when using the project-based learning method, the author can derive the concept of project-based teaching as follows: "Project-based teaching is a teaching method in which students perform a complex learning task,

combining theory and practice to create a product" (Nguyen Huu Hop, 2018).

This concept emphasizes the applicability of the project-based method, where students not only learn theory but also apply knowledge to real-world situations by carrying out complex tasks. The combination of theory and practice helps students develop both their thinking and skills, while the final product of the learning process also reflects the students' level of understanding and ability to apply their knowledge.

- **Practical Orientation:** The topic of the project stems from real-life situations in society, professional practices, and daily life. The tasks of the project must address issues that are appropriate for the learners' level and cognitive abilities. Learning projects with practical social significance help connect classroom learning with real-life and societal practices. In ideal situations, the implementation of projects can have a positive social impact.

Learner Engagement Orientation: Students are involved in selecting topics and learning content that match their abilities and personal interests. Furthermore, the learners' interest should continue to develop throughout the process of carrying out the project.

Complexity and Interdisciplinary Approach: The content of the project integrates knowledge from various fields or subjects to solve a complex task or problem.

Action-Oriented Approach: During the project implementation, there is a combination of theoretical research and the application of theory into practical activities. This approach helps test, reinforce, and expand theoretical knowledge, while also developing action skills and real-life experience for the learners.

Learner Autonomy: In project-based learning, students are required to actively and independently participate in all stages of the learning process. This approach encourages and demands responsibility and creativity from the learners. The teacher mainly plays the role of a consultant, guide, and helper. However, the level of autonomy should be appropriate to the

students' experience, abilities, and the difficulty level of the tasks.

Collaboration: Learning projects are often carried out in groups, where there is collaboration and task division among group members. Project-based learning demands and fosters the readiness and skills for teamwork, not only among students but also between students and teachers, as well as with other social entities involved in the project. This characteristic is also known as social learning.

Product Orientation: During the project implementation, the outcomes are not limited to theoretical knowledge but, in most cases, involve the creation of tangible products from practical activities. These products can be used, presented, or published.

The Process of Implementing Project-Based Learning

From the perspective of students' psychological development during the learning process, Kilpatrick proposed a theory of project-based learning consisting of four distinct steps: 1. Setting Learning Outcomes to motivate students to engage in a project and be ready to achieve a specific goal through their activities. 2. Planning activities consciously at an individual level. 3. Practical activities to achieve the set goal, which should be feasible. 4. Evaluating the results achieved.

Kilpatrick argued that a learning activity cannot be motivated if students do not know what the object of motivation is. Planning and executing an activity cannot be realized without a clear, conscious goal that students are aiming toward. If students wish to evaluate something, they must have a reference point for what is being evaluated, i.e., the goal set for the activity. If students act to achieve the set goal, it is considered learning, as defined by Kilpatrick (1918).

An example of learning with physical activity linked to a process, where students create a kite, can be presented according to Kilpatrick's project-based learning theory:

- **Stage 1:** Setting the Learning Outcomes is to create a kite and make it fly.

- **Stage 2:** Planning involves figuring out how to make the kite correctly, what knowledge and skills are required, and how to ensure the kite can fly.
- **Stage 3:** Implementation involves thinking about the characteristics of the kite and finding ways to achieve the desired outcome. Students take action based on their exploration to make the kite fly, creating a sense of satisfaction.
- **Stage 4:** Evaluation assesses the results of the process, where the creation of the kite is described as the learning process itself.

Applying the Project-Based Learning Method in Organizing the Teaching of Educational Economics

Based on the cognitive development process of students according to Kilpatrick's project-based learning theory, which follows four steps: setting the goal, planning, implementing the plan to achieve the goal, and evaluating personal satisfaction with the goal achieved; considering the teacher's role in organizing the teaching process so that students can develop according to the steps outlined in Kilpatrick's theory; and considering the characteristics of the project-based method in organizing teaching, the following process for organizing the teaching of Educational Economics using the project-based method is proposed:

Figure 1. Illustrates the Process of Organizing Educational Activities Based on the Project-Based Method, which Includes Three Main Stage

Stage 1: Setting the Learning Outcomes: Organize group discussions for students to identify the goals they need to achieve from the assigned tasks.

Stage 2: Implementing the Project: In this step, the teacher carries out three tasks to implement the project as follows:

- **Step 1:** The teacher assigns the task to the students. Based on the characteristics of the project and the lesson objectives, the teacher sets a task that aligns with students' experience and interests, fits the available technical resources, and adheres to the allowed time frame. Several ideas may be proposed from real-world situations, creating a problem or task that needs to be solved (Nguyen Huu Hop, 2018).

- **Step 2:** The teacher guides students in developing a plan: identifying the tasks required to achieve the project's goal and determining the knowledge and skills necessary to complete these tasks and achieve the set objectives.

- **Step 3:** The teacher observes students as they carry out the project. Students apply theory to perform the tasks they have proposed, leading to the creation of the project's product. The product can be a report, an article, or a physical artifact. Based on the results achieved from the task, students gain knowledge, skills, and experience to improve their ability to complete similar tasks in the future.

Stage 3: Evaluating the Product: Based on the product the students have completed, the

teacher analyzes the strengths and weaknesses in the process of applying theory to the creation of the product. This evaluation highlights both the successful and the incomplete aspects of the product, providing students with the opportunity to refine their knowledge and skills.

Applying Project-Based Learning in Teaching Educational Economics for Students in Education

Educational Economics Teaching Theory

Objectives of Educational Economics (Trương Thi Thuy Hang- Dương Thi Hoang Yen, 2014):

- Analyze methods for planning, financing, and education costs.
- Analyze the relationship between the education system and economic and educational development.
- Analyze educational issues within the context of economic concepts.

Table 1. Learning Outcomes

Learning Outcomes	
Knowledge	Describe the tasks, subjects, and research methods in educational economics.
	Analyze the relationship between economics and education, as well as fundamental issues in educational economics.
	Analyze educational investment globally and in Vietnam.
Skills	Plan educational finances and costs.
	Assess investment effectiveness.
Autonomy and Responsibility	Fulfill roles and responsibilities in participating in educational projects.

Applying Project-Based Learning in Teaching Educational Economics

In applying project-based learning to the Educational Economics course, we implement educational financial planning and investment effectiveness evaluation through a three-stage process with specific activities as follows:

Table 2. Educational Financial Planning and Investment Effectiveness Evaluation through a Three-Stage Process with Specific Activities

Process	Teacher Activities	Student Activities	Transformation Purpose
<i>Project 1: Financial Planning and Cost Estimation for Educational Projects</i>			
Learning Outcomes	<p>Present the basic principles of financial planning for educational projects, including expenses, funding sources, and budgeting.</p> <p>Develop a financial plan for practical educational projects.</p> <p>Analyze and forecast costs in educational projects, thereby creating effective financial strategies.</p> <p>Emphasize responsibility and caution when planning finances for educational projects.</p>	Group Discussion and Task Identification	Determine the learner requirements for implementing the project.
Project Implementation	<p>Assign tasks</p> <p>Grouping: Divide the class into groups to work together on the assigned tasks.</p> <p>Task: Identify the tasks needed for financial planning in projects, such as project selection, cost forecasting in educational projects, and creating effective financial strategies.</p>	Students listen to tasks, identify tasks needed to complete the assignment.	Determine necessary knowledge in financial planning for educational projects, including expenses, funding sources, and budgeting.
	<p>Guide students in creating a plan</p> <p>Identify necessary knowledge and skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Principles of financial management, budget planning, and methods of calculating costs for educational projects. 	<p>Group discussion to determine the order of each task.</p> <p>Assign members to carry out each task</p>	<p>Develop financial plans for real-life education projects.</p> <p>Analyze and forecast costs in education</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guide students in using financial management software and creating financial reports. - Organize group discussions on financial issues in educational projects. 	according to their individual abilities. Develop a plan for task execution.	projects to devise effective financial strategies.
	Facilitate each member in performing their tasks; if any member encounters difficulties, they should independently contact the teacher for assistance	Each member performs their tasks according to the specified timeline.	Responsibility and caution in financial planning for educational projects.
Evaluate learning outcomes	Evaluate the accuracy and feasibility of the financial plan. Evaluate the creativity and effectiveness of the proposed financial solutions.	Write a financial report, present the budget and financial solutions to the class.	The transformation results achieve the objectives.
Project 2: Evaluate the effectiveness of educational investment.			
Learning Outcomes	<p>Present methods for evaluating the effectiveness of educational investment, including indicators for measuring education quality and the impact of investment.</p> <p>Use cost-benefit analysis tools to measure the effectiveness of educational investment. Show respect in evaluating and improving the effectiveness of educational investment.</p>	Group discussion to identify tasks to be carried out	Identify the learner's requirements that need to be met for project implementation.
Project Implementation	Introduce tools and methods for evaluating the effectiveness of educational investment. Guide students on how to use effectiveness measurement indicators and data analysis methods.	Students listen to the task and identify the work required to complete it	Identify the necessary knowledge in evaluating educational investment.
	<p>Provide real-life scenarios:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investment in educational facilities - Investment in teacher training - Investment in marketing in education 	Learn the cost-benefit method to evaluate the effectiveness of educational investment programs.	Be able to use cost-benefit analysis tools to measure the effectiveness of educational investment.
	Facilitate each member in performing their tasks; if any member encounters difficulties, they should independently contact the teacher for assistance.	Each member performs their tasks according to the specified timeline.	Show respect in evaluating and improving the effectiveness of educational investment.
Evaluate learning outcomes	Evaluate the ability to use investment effectiveness analysis tools. Evaluate the level of creativity and the ability to propose improvements.	Write a financial report, present the budget and financial solutions to the class.	The transformation results achieve the objectives.

Conclusion

Research shows that applying the project method to teaching the Economics of Education has a positive impact on developing financial and cost planning skills for educational projects and evaluating investment effectiveness in education. Teaching activities using the project method can be conducted outside the classroom

environment, creating a change in the learning environment that enhances students' learning enthusiasm. The project method is often organized in a group work format, where students learn to work like researchers, using tools that foster cooperation and creativity through the process of producing a product. Students have the opportunity to present their work, which helps them develop presentation

skills and the ability to analyze the value of their products. However, every teaching method has its strengths and weaknesses; this study focuses on the strengths that promote students' active engagement in learning and the opportunity to integrate knowledge from various subjects while completing tasks to produce a final product. To use the project method effectively and limit its weaknesses, such as the time it consumes and the difficulty in accurately assessing individual abilities after the product is completed, instructors need to follow the three-step process outlined above, choose projects that match students' characteristics and abilities, and connect them with real-life and future career relevance.

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